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PSP-21

BOTULINUM TOKSIN – OTROV, LEK I KOZMETIČKO SREDSTVO

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Clostridium botulinum je G+, anaerobna bakterija i njene se spore nalaze u zemlji i vodi. Spore mogu biti prisutne u voću, povrću i morskim plodovima. Bakterija proizvodi botulinum toksin, koji se smatra jednim od najjačih i najopasnijih bioloških otrova poznatih čovečanstvu jer ovaj neurotoksin inhibiše oslobađanje acetilholina i svoj paralitički efekat ostvaruje brzom, ireverzibilnom blokadom neuromišićne transmisije, izazivajući paralizu zahvaćenih mišića. Izlaganjem uticaju ovog neurotoksina razvija se botulizam. Identifikovano je 7 serotipova botulinum toksina (A, B, C [C1, C2], D, E, F i G), strukturno sličnih, ali antigenski i serološki različitih. Botulizam je kod ljudi najčešće uzrokovan neurotoksinima tipa A, B, E, retko neurotoksinom F. Tipovi C i D izazivaju toksičnost kod životinja. Botulizam se manifestuje u vidu muke, povraćanja, otežanog gutanja, duplog viđenja i suvoće usta. Dodatne neurološke manifestacije uključuju paralizu koja može dovesti do prestanka disanja. Terapija je urgentna primena polivalentnog antitoksičnog seruma koji je efikasan protiv svih 7 serotipova toksina. No i pored svih toksičnih efekata botulinskog toksina na ljudski ili životinjski organizam, nalazi veliku primenu u medicini formulisan u obliku injekcija za terapiju različitih vrsta distonija poput: spastične, cervikalne, laringealne kao i generalizovane, te kod blefarospazma, hiperhidroze, strabizma i ptoze, za terapiju tremora kod Parkinsonove bolesti, kod glavobolje i urinarne inkontinencije. Injekcije botulinskog toksina se obično dobro podnose nakon injektovanja nakon čega toksin prolazi u mišiće i druge tkiva. Razvojem novih farmaceutskih formulacija ovog neurotoksina, počela je njegova primena i u kozmetologiji za korekciju bora u predelu gornje trećine lica radi relaksacije mišića pri čemu sprečava njihovu kontrakciju. Zbog sve češće pojave falsifikovanih ampula botulinum toksina, veoma je važno koristiti proizvode koji su registrovani za predviđene indikacije.

Ključne reči: Clostridium Botulinum , botulinum toksin, botulizam

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BOTULINUM TOXIN – POISON, MEDICINE AND COSMETIC PREPARATION

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Clostridium botulinum is G +, anaerobic bacteria and its spores are found in the soil, water, can also be present in fruits, vegetables and seafood. The bacteria produces a botulinum toxin, which is considered one of the strongest and most dangerous biological poisons known to mankind since inhibits the release of acetylcholine and achieves its paralytic effect by a rapid, irreversible blockage of neuromuscular transmission, which causes paralysis of the affected muscles. Botulism develops by exposing the influence of this neurotoxin. 7 serotypes of botulinum toxin (A, B, C [C1, C2], D, E, F and G) were identified, structurally similar, but antigenic and serologically different. Botulism is most commonly caused in humans by neurotoxins of type A, B, E, rarely by neurotoxin F. Types C and D cause toxicity in animals. Exposition to this neurotoxin causes botulism. Botulism is manifested in the form of pain, vomiting, difficulty swallowing, double vision and dry mouth. Additional neurological manifestations include paralysis that can lead to breathing failure. Therapy is an urgent application of a polyvalent antitoxic serum that is effective against all 7 serotypes of toxins. But despite all the toxic effects of botulinum toxin on the human or animal organism, there is a great application in medicine formulated in the form of injections for the therapy of various types of dystonia such as: spastic, cervical, laryngeal, and generalized, and in blepharospasm, hyperhidrosis, strabismus and ptosis, and for the treatment of tremors in Parkinson's disease, headache and urinary incontinence. Injections of botulinum toxin are usually well tolerated after injection, after which the toxin passes into the muscles and other tissues. By developing new pharmaceutical formulations of this neurotoxin, its application began in cosmetology for the correction of wrinkles in the upper third part of the face for the relaxation of muscles, preventing their contraction. Due to the increasingly frequent occurrence of counterfeit botulinum toxin ampoules, it is very important to use products that are registered for the intended indications.

Key words: *Clostridium Botulinum* , botulinum toxin, botulism

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